

4-Remainder Cordial Labeling of Some Graphs

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Abstract: Let G be a (p, q) graph. Let f be a function from $V(G)$ to the set $\{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ where k is an integer $2 < k \leq |V(G)|$. For each edge uv assign the label r where r is the remainder when $f(u)$ is divided by $f(v)$ (or) $f(v)$ is divided by $f(u)$ according as $f(u) \geq f(v)$ or $f(v) \geq f(u)$. f is called a k -remainder cordial labeling of G if $|v_f(i) - v_f(j)| \leq 1$, $i, j \in \{1, \dots, k\}$, where $v_f(x)$ denote the number of vertices labeled with x and $|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \leq 1$ where $e_f(0)$ and $e_f(1)$ respectively denote the number of edges labeled with even integers and number of edges labelled with odd integers. A graph with admits a k -remainder cordial labeling is called a k -remainder cordial graph. In this paper we investigate the 4- remainder cordial behavior of grid, subdivision of crown, Subdivision of bistar, book, Jelly fish, subdivision of Jelly fish, Mongolian tent graphs.

Key Words: k -Remainder cordial labeling, Smarandache k -remainder cordial labeling, grid, subdivision of crown, subdivision of bistar, book, Jelly fish, subdivision of Jelly fish, Mongolian tent.

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§1. Introduction

We considered only finite and simple graphs. The subdivision graph $S(G)$ of a graph G is obtained by replacing each edge uv by a path uvw . The product graph $G_1 \times G_2$ is defined as follows:

Consider any two points $u = (u_1, u_2)$ and $v = (v_1, v_2)$ in $V = V_1 \times V_2$. Then u and v are adjacent in $G_1 \times G_2$ whenever $[u_1 = v_1$ and u_2 adj $v_2]$ or $[u_2 = v_2$ and u_1 adj $v_1]$. The graph $P_m \times P_n$ is called the planar grid. Let G_1, G_2 respectively be $(p_1, q_1), (p_2, q_2)$ graphs. The corona of G_1 with G_2 , $G_1 \odot G_2$ is the graph obtained by taking one copy of G_1 and p_1 copies of G_2 and joining the i^{th} vertex of G_1 with an edge to every vertex in the i^{th} copy of G_2 . A mongolian tent $M_{m,n}$ is a graph obtained from $P_m \times P_n$ by adding one extra vertex above the grid and joining every other of the top row of $P_m \times P_n$ to the new vertex. Cahit [1], introduced the concept of cordial labeling of graphs. Ponraj et al. [4, 6], introduced remainder cordial labeling of graphs and investigate the remainder cordial labeling behavior of path, cycle,

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star, bistar, complete graph, $S(K_{1,n})$, $S(B_{n,n})$, $S(W_n)$, P_n^2 , $P_n^2 \cup K_{1,n}$, $P_n^2 \cup B_{n,n}$, $P_n \cup B_{n,n}$, $P_n \cup K_{1,n}$, $K_{1,n} \cup S(K_{1,n})$, $K_{1,n} \cup S(B_{n,n})$, $S(K_{1,n}) \cup S(B_{n,n})$, etc., and also the concept of k -remainder cordial labeling introduced in [5]. In this paper we investigate the 4-remainder cordial labeling behavior of Grid, Subdivision of crown, Subdivision of bistar, Book, Jelly fish, Subdivision of Jelly fish, Mongolian tent, etc,. Terms are not defined here follows from Harary [3] and Gallian [2].

§2. k -Remainder Cordial Labeling

Definition 2.1 Let G be a (p, q) graph. Let f be a function from $V(G)$ to the set $\{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ where k is an integer $2 < k \leq |V(G)|$. For each edge uv assign the label r where r is the remainder when $f(u)$ is divided by $f(v)$ (or) $f(v)$ is divided by $f(u)$ according as $f(u) \geq f(v)$ or $f(v) \geq f(u)$. The labeling f is called a k -remainder cordial labeling of G if $|v_f(i) - v_f(j)| \leq 1$ and $|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \leq 1$, otherwise, Smarandachely if $|v_f(i) - v_f(j)| \geq 1$ or $|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \geq 1$ for integers $i, j \in \{1, \dots, k\}$, where $v_f(x)$ and $e_f(0)$, $e_f(1)$ respectively denote the number of vertices labeled with x , the number of edges labeled with even integers and the number of edges labelled with odd integers. Such a graph with a k -remainder cordial labeling is called a k -remainder cordial graph.

First we investigate the 4-remainder cordial labeling behavior of the planar grid.

Theorem 2.2 The planar grid $P_m \times P_n$ is 4-remainder cordial.

Proof Clearly this grid has m -rows and n -columns. We assign the labels to the vertices by row wise.

Case 1. $m \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$

Let $m = 4t$. Then assign the label 1 to the vertices of $1^{st}, 2^{nd}, \dots, t^{th}$ rows. Next we move to the $(t+1)^{th}$ row. Assign the label 4 to the vertices of $(t+1)^{th}, (t+2)^{th}, \dots, (2t)^{th}$ rows. Next assign the label to the vertices $(2t+1)^{th}$ row. Assign the labels 2 and 3 alternatively to the vertices of $(2t+1)^{th}$ row. Next move to $(2t+2)^{th}$ row. Assign the labels 3 and 2 alternatively to the vertices of $(2t+2)^{th}$ row. In general i^{th} row is called as in the $(i-2)^{th}$ row, where $2t+1 \leq i \leq 3t$. This procedure continued until we reach the $(4t)^{th}$ row.

Case 2. $m \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$

As in Case 1, assign the labels to the vertices of the first, second, $\dots, (m-1)^{th}$ row. We give the label to the m^{th} row as in given below.

Subcase 2.1 $n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$

Rotate the row and column and result follows from Case 1.

Subcase 2.2 $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$

Assign the labels 4, 3, 4, 3, $\dots, 4, 3$ to the vertices of the first, second, $\dots, (\frac{n-1}{2})^{th}$ columns. Next assign the label 2 to the vertices of $(\frac{n+1}{2})^{th}$ column. Then next assign the labels 2, 1, 2, 1, $\dots,$

2, 1 to the vertices of $\frac{n+3}{2}, \frac{n+5}{2}, \dots, (\frac{2n}{2} - 2)^{th}$ columns. Assign the remaining vertices.

Subcase 2.3 $n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$

Assign the labels 4, 3, 4, 3, \dots , 4, 3 to the vertices of $1^{st}, 2^{nd}, \dots, (\frac{n-2}{2})^{th}$ columns. Next assign the label 2 to the vertices of $(\frac{n}{2})^{th}$ column. Then next assign the labels 2, 1, 2, 1, \dots , 2, 1 to the vertices of $\frac{n}{2}+1, \frac{n}{2}+2, \dots, (\frac{2n}{2} - 1)^{th}$ columns. Finally assign the label 1 to the remaining vertices of n^{th} column.

Subcase 2.4 $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$

Assign the labels 4, 3, 4, 3, \dots , 4, 3 alternatively to the vertices of $1^{st}, 2^{nd}, \dots, (\frac{n+1}{2})^{th}$ columns. Then next assign the labels 1, 2, 1, 2, \dots to the vertices of $\frac{n+3}{2}, \frac{n+5}{2}, \dots, (\frac{2n}{2} - 1)^{th}$ columns. Finally assign the label 1 to the remaining vertices of n^{th} column. Hence f is a 4-remainder cordial labeling of $P_m \times P_n$.

All other cases follow by symmetry. \square

Next is the graph $K_2 + mK_1$.

Theorem 2.3 *If $m \equiv 0, 1, 3 \pmod{4}$ then $K_2 + mK_1$ is 4-remainder cordial.*

Proof It is easy to verify that $K_2 + mK_1$ has $m + 2$ vertices and $2m$ edges. Let $V(K_2 + mK_1) = \{u, u_i, v : 1 \leq i \leq m\}$ and $E(K_2 + mK_1) = \{uv, uu_i, vu_i : 1 \leq i \leq m\}$.

Case 1. $m \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$

Let $m = 4t$. Then assign the label 3, 3 respectively to the vertices u, v . Next assign the label 1 to the vertices u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{t+1} . Then next assign the label 2 to the vertices $u_{t+2}, u_{t+3}, \dots, u_{2t+1}$. Then followed by assign the label 3 to the vertices $u_{2t+2}, u_{2t+3}, \dots, u_{3t}$. Finally assign the label 4 to the remaining non-labelled vertices $u_{3t+1}, u_{3t+2}, \dots, u_{4t}$.

Case 2. $m \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$

As in Case 1, assign the labels to the vertices $u, v, u_i, (1 \leq i \leq m - 1)$. Next assign the label 2 to the vertex u_m .

Case 3. $m \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$

Assign the labels to the vertices $u, v, u_i, (1 \leq i \leq m - 2)$ as in case(ii). Finally assign the labels 3, 4 respectively to the vertices u_{m-1}, u_m . The table given below establish that this labeling f is a 4-remainder cordial labeling.

Nature of m	$e_f(0)$	$e_f(1)$
$m \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$	$m + 1$	m
$m \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$	m	$m + 1$
$m \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$	m	$m + 1$

Table 1

This completes the proof. \square

The next graph is the book graph B_n .

Theorem 2.4 *The book B_n is 4-remainder cordial for all n .*

Proof Let $V(B_n) = \{u, v, u_i, v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ and $E(B_n) = \{uv, uu_i, vv_i, u_i v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$.

Case 1. n is even

Assign the labels 3, 4 to the vertices u and v respectively. Assign the label 1 to the vertices $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{\frac{n}{2}}$ and assign 4 to the vertices $u_{\frac{n}{2}+1}, u_{\frac{n}{2}+2}, \dots, u_n$. Next we consider the vertices v_i . Assign the label 2 to the vertices $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{\frac{n}{2}}$. Next assign the label 3 to the remaining vertices $v_{\frac{n}{2}+1}, v_{\frac{n}{2}+2}, \dots, v_n$, respectively.

Case 2. n is odd

Assign the labels 3, 4 to the vertices u and v respectively. Fix the labels 4, 2, 1 to the vertices $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{\frac{n}{2}+1}$ and also fix the labels 3, 1, 2 respectively to the vertices $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{\frac{n}{2}+1}$. Assign the labels to the vertices u_4, u_5, \dots, u_n as in the sequence 2, 1, 2, 1, ..., 2, 1. In similar fashion, assign the labels to the vertices v_4, v_5, \dots, v_n as in the sequence 3, 4, 3, 4, ..., 3, 4. The table 2 shows that this vertex labeling f is a 4-remainder cordial labeling.

Nature of n	$e_f(0)$	$e_f(1)$
n is even	$m + 1$	m
n is odd	m	$m + 1$

Table 2

This completes the proof. □

Now we consider the subdivision of $B_{n,n}$.

Theorem 2.5 *The subdivision of $B_{n,n}$ is 4-remainder cordial.*

Proof Let $V(S(B_{n,n})) = \{u, v, u_i, v_i, w_i, x, x_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ and $E(S(B_{n,n})) = \{uu_i, vv_i, u_i w_i, v_i x_i, ux, xv : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$. It is clearly to verify that $S(B_{n,n})$ has $4n + 3$ vertices and $4n + 2$ edges.

Assign the labels 1, 4, 3 to the vertices u, x and v respectively. Assign the labels 1, 3 alternatively to the vertices u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n . Next assign the labels 2, 4 alternatively to the vertices w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n . We now consider the vertices v_i and x_i . Assign the labels 2, 4 alternatively to the vertices v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n . Then finally assign the labels 3, 1 alternatively to the vertices x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n . Obviously this vertex labeling is a 4-remainder cordial labeling. □

Next, we consider the subdivision of crown graph.

Theorem 2.5 *The subdivision of $C_n \odot K_1$ is 4-remainder cordial.*

Proof Let $u_1 u_2 \dots u_n$ be a cycle C_n . Let $V(C_n \odot K_1) = V(C_n \cup \{v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\})$ and $E(C_n \odot K_1) = E(C_n \cup \{u_i v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\})$. The subdivide edges $u_i u_{i+1}$ and $u_i v_i$ by x_i and y_i respectively. Assign the label 2 to the vertices $u_i, (1 \leq i \leq n)$ and 3 to the vertices

$x_i, (1 \leq i \leq n)$. Next assign the label 1 to the vertices $y_i, (1 \leq i \leq n)$. Finally assign the label 4 to the vertices $v_i, (1 \leq i \leq n)$. Clearly, this labeling f is a 4-remainder cordial labeling. \square

Now we consider the Jelly fish $J(m, n)$.

Theorem 2.6 *The Jelly fish $J(m, n)$ is 4-remainder cordial.*

Proof Let $V(J(m, n)) = \{u, v, x, y, u_i, v_j : 1 \leq i \leq m \text{ and } 1 \leq j \leq n\}$ and $E(J(m, n)) = \{uu_i, vv_j, ux, uy, vx, vy : 1 \leq i \leq m \text{ and } 1 \leq j \leq n\}$. Clearly $J(m, n)$ has $m + n + 4$ vertices and $m + n + 5$ edges.

Case 1. $m = n$ and m is even.

Assign the label 2 to the vertices $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{\frac{m}{2}}$ and assign the label 4 to the vertices $u_{\frac{m}{2}+1}, u_{\frac{m}{2}+2}, \dots, u_n$. Next assign the label 1 to the vertices $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{\frac{m}{2}}$ and assign 3 to the vertices $v_{\frac{m}{2}+1}, v_{\frac{m}{2}+2}, \dots, v_n$. Finally assign the labels 3, 4, 2, 1 respectively to the vertices u, x, y, v .

Case 2. $m = n$ and m is odd.

In this case assign the labels to the vertices $u_i, v_i (1 \leq i \leq m - 1)$ and u, v, x, y as in Case 1. Next assign the labels 2, 1 respectively to the vertices u_n and v_n .

Case 3. $m \neq n$ and assume $m > n$.

Assign the labels 3, 4, 1, 2 to the vertices u, x, y, v respectively. As in Case 1 and 2, assign the labels to the vertices $u_i, v_i (1 \leq i \leq n)$.

Subcase 3.1 $m - n$ is even. Assign the labels to the vertices $u_{n+1}, u_{n+2}, \dots, u_m$ as in the sequence 3, 4, 2, 1; 3, 4, 2, 1; \dots . It is easy to verify that u_n is received the label 1 if $m - n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$.

Subcase 3.2 $m - n$ is odd. Assign the labels to the vertices $u_i (n \leq i \leq m)$ as in the sequence 4, 3, 2, 1; 4, 3, 2, 1; \dots . Clearly, u_n is received the label 1 if $m - n \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$. \square

For illustration, a 4-remainder cordial labeling of Jelly fish $J(m, n)$ is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1

Theorem 2.8 *The subdivision of the Jelly fish $J(m, n)$ is 4-remainder cordial.*

Proof Let $V(S(J(m, n))) = \{u, u_i, x_i, v, v_j, y_j : 1 \leq i \leq m, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{w_i : 1 \leq i \leq 7\}$ and $E(S(J(m, n))) = \{uu_i, u_i x_i, vv_j, v_j y_j : 1 \leq i \leq m, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{uw_1, uw_2, w_1 w_5, w_5 w_6, w_6 w_7, w_5 w_3, w_3 v, v w_4, w_4 w_7, w_2 w_7\}$.

Case 1. $m = n$.

Assign the label 2 to the vertices u_1, u_2, \dots, u_m and 3 to the vertices x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m . Next assign the label 1 to the vertices v_1, v_2, \dots, v_m and assign the label 4 to the vertices y_1, y_2, \dots, y_m . Finally assign the labels 3, 2, 3, 2, 3, 1, 4, 4 and 1 respectively to the vertices $u, w_1, w_5, w_6, w_7, w_2, w_3, v$ and w_4 .

Case 2. $m > n$.

Assign the labels to the vertices $u, u_i, v, v_i, x_i, y_i, w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4, w_5, w_6, w_7, (1 \leq i \leq n)$ as in case(i). Next assign the labels 1, 4 to the next two vertices x_{n+1}, x_{n+2} respectively. Then next assign the labels 1, 4 respectively to the vertices x_{n+3}, x_{n+4} . Proceeding like this until we reach the vertex x_n . That is the vertices $x_{n+1}, x_{n+2}, x_{n+3}, x_{n+4}, \dots$ are labelled in the pattern 1, 4; 1, 4; 1, 4; 1, 4; \dots . Similarly the vertices u_{n+1}, u_{n+2}, \dots are labelled as 2, 3; 2, 3; 2, 3; \dots , 2, 3. The Table 3, establish that this vertex labeling f is a 4-remainder cordial labeling of $S(J(m, n))$.

Nature of m and n	$e_f(0)$	$e_f(1)$
$m = n$	$2n + 5$	$2n + 5$
$m > n$	$m + n + 5$	$m + n + 5$

This completes the proof. □

Theorem 2.9 *The graph $C_3^{(t)}$ is 4-remainder cordial.*

Proof Let $V(C_3^{(t)}) = \{u, u_i, v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ and $E(C_3^{(t)}) = \{uu_i, vv_i, u_i v_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$. Assume $t \geq 3$. Fix the label 3 to the central vertex u and fix the labels 1, 2, 2, 4, 3, 4 respectively to the vertices u_1, u_2, u_3, v_1, v_2 and v_3 . Next assign the labels 1, 2 to the vertices u_4, u_5 . Then assign the labels 1, 2 respectively to the next two vertices u_6, u_7 and so on. That is the vertices u_4, u_5, u_6, u_7 are labelled as in the pattern 1, 2, 1, 2 \dots , 1, 2. Note that the vertex u_n received the label 1 or 2 according as n is even or odd. In a similar way assign the labels to the vertices v_4, v_5, v_6, v_7 as in the sequence 4, 3, 4, 3, 4, 3, \dots . Clearly 4 is the label of u_n according as n is even or odd. The Table 4 establish that this vertex labeling is a 4-remainder cordial labeling of $C_3^{(t)}$, $t \geq 3$.

Nature of n	$e_f(0)$	$e_f(1)$
n is even	$\frac{3n}{2}$	$\frac{3n}{2}$
n is odd	$n + 1$	$n + 2$

Table 4

For $t = 1, 2$ the remainder cordial labeling of graphs $C_3^{(1)}$ and $C_3^{(2)}$ are given below in Figure 2.

Figure 2

This completes the proof. □

Theorem 2.10 *The Mongolian tent $M_{m,n}$ is 4-remainder cordial.*

Proof Assign the label 3 to the new vertex.

Case 1. $m \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$ and $n \equiv 0, 2 \pmod{4}$.

Consider the first row of M_n . Assign the labels $2, 3, 2, 3, \dots, 2, 3$ to the vertices in the first row. Next assign the labels $3, 2, 3, 2, \dots, 3, 2$ to the vertices in the second row. This procedure is continue until reach the $\frac{n}{2}^{th}$ row. Next assign the labels $1, 4, 1, 4, \dots, 1, 4$ to the vertices in the $\frac{n}{2} + 1^{th}$ row. Then next assign the labels $4, 1, 4, 1, \dots, 4, 1$ to the vertices in the $\frac{n}{2} + 2^{th}$ row. This proceedings like this assign the labels continue until reach the last row.

Case 2. $m \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$ and $n \equiv 0, 2 \pmod{4}$.

In this case assign the labels to the vertices as in Case 1.

Case 3. $m \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ and $n \equiv 0, 2 \pmod{4}$.

Here assign the labels by column wise to the vertices of M_n . Assign the labels $2, 3, 2, 3, \dots, 2, 3$ to the vertices in the first column. Next assign the labels $3, 2, 3, 2, \dots, 3, 2$ to the vertices in the second column. This method is continue until reach the $\frac{n}{2}^{th}$ column. Next assign the labels $1, 4, 1, 4, \dots, 1, 4$ to the vertices in the $\frac{n}{2} + 1^{th}$ column. Then next assign the labels $4, 1, 4, 1, \dots, 4, 1$ to the vertices in the $\frac{n}{2} + 2^{th}$ column. This procedure is continue until reach the last column.

Case 4. $m \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$ and $n \equiv 0, 2 \pmod{4}$.

As in Case 3 assign the labels to the vertices in this case. The remainder cordial labeling of graphs $M_{7,4}$ is given below in Figure 3..

Figure 3

This completes the proof. □

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